

STATIC AND FATIGUE DELAMINATION FROM DISCONTINUOUS PLYS – EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATIONS

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SUMMARY

Cut ply specimens of IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy laminates were tested under monotonic and cyclic tensile loading. Experimental results were used to validate new cohesive interface element formulations for static and fatigue delamination. Results are presented in terms of static failure loads and fatigue crack growth rates.

Keywords: Delamination, static, fatigue, ply termination, cohesive interface element.

INTRODUCTION

The manufacture of laminated composite tapered sections often involves the inclusion of ply terminations so that gradual reductions in thickness can be achieved. Ply discontinuities generate stress concentrations which may cause delamination to initiate, be it under quasi-static, impact or fatigue loading. During the design stage, it is important to consider the strain energy release rate (SERR) associated with ply terminations within a structure, taking into account in-service loading and environmental conditions. Ideally, design decisions should be made in ways that minimise the SERR, so that the final structure is less prone to delamination damage.

There is a strong need for predictive models which could assist the design of composite parts in an industrial setting. The present work aims at providing validated predictive modelling capabilities for the delamination damage under quasi-static and fatigue loading. This paper focuses on the experimental measurement of delamination properties for a carbon-fibre/epoxy prepreg system, as well as the development of predictive models for analysing static and fatigue-driven delamination.

The testing programme consisted of quasi-static and constant-amplitude cyclic loading of laminated specimens with central discontinuous plies, following the procedure described previously for glass-fibre/epoxy laminates [1]. The predictive modelling capability is based on the application of novel cohesive element formulations for modelling delamination under quasi-static and cyclic loading in a finite element analysis

framework. This paper describes the development and implementation of these tools as well as their validation against experimental observations.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Laminated specimens containing central discontinuous plies provide simple and effective mode-II delamination tests when loaded in uniaxial tension [1]. All specimens analysed in this work were manufactured from Hexcel® IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy prepreg with a nominal ply cured thickness of 0.127 mm. Unidirectional specimens containing eight continuous plies and two central cut plies were manufactured from larger plates and cured in an autoclave. Glass/epoxy end tabs were adhesively bonded to these plates, and specimens were cut down to the dimensions shown in Figure 1. All tests (quasi-static and fatigue loading) were performed in tension which resulted in pure mode-II delamination. An Instron servo-hydraulic testing machine fitted with a load cell of 100 kN was used for the entire experimental programme, and the test setup can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Cut-ply specimen: (a) geometry and (b) detail of the central discontinuous plies.

Quasi-static tests

Quasi-static tests were performed under displacement control with a fixed crosshead velocity of 0.5 mm/min. Results are presented in Figure 3 as curves of net section stress normalised by the experimental average failure stress versus crosshead displacement normalised by the initial gauge length. Static failure loads were taken as the maximum force prior to the first load drop. Post failure investigation showed that specimens failed by delamination starting at the discontinuity and propagating towards the end tabs. The average net section failure stress (which takes into account only the thickness of continuous plies) was 1932.3 MPa with a coefficient of variation of 2.1% for five repeats.

Figure 2: Fatigue testing of cut-ply specimens, (a) overall setup and (b) detail of the clip gauge extensometer.

Figure 3: Normalised net section stress versus normalised crosshead displacement for quasi-static cut ply tests.

The strain energy release rate associated with cut ply delamination was obtained via the closed-form solution proposed in [1],

$$G = \frac{\sigma_{net}^2 (h-t)t}{4E_{11}h}, \quad (1)$$

where σ_{net} is the average net section stress, h is the total specimen thickness, t is the thickness of discontinuous plies, and E_{11} is the elastic modulus in the fibre direction. The average value obtained from these experimental results was 1.18 N/mm.

Cyclic tests

Cyclic tests were performed under controlled sinusoidal load. A clip-gauge extensometer was used to record strains in the direction of loading. The test *severity* is defined here as the ratio between the maximum applied net section stress and the average failure stress under static loading. The load ratio, or R-ratio, is defined by,

$$R = F_{min} / F_{max} , \quad (2)$$

where F_{max} is the peak force and F_{min} is the trough force in a cyclic regime. Due to the quadratic dependency of G on the applied stress, equation (1), for positive values of R we have,

$$\Delta G = (1 - R^2) G_{max} , \quad (3)$$

where G_{max} is the strain energy release rate at peak load.

Peak forces were chosen based on the application of different load severities, and three different load ratios were applied. Loading frequencies were adjusted in order to keep a constant stress rate between all tests, with the baseline frequency being 5 Hz for the 75% severity case. The experimental matrix of cyclic tests is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Cyclic test details.

R-ratio	Severity	Peak net section stress	Trough net section stress	Frequency
	[%]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[Hz]
0.1	75	1449.2	144.9	5.000
0.1	70	1352.6	135.3	5.357
0.1	60	1159.4	115.9	6.250
0.1	50	966.2	96.6	7.500
0.1	40	772.9	77.3	9.375
0.3	50	1352.6	405.8	6.888
0.3	50	1159.4	347.8	8.036
0.3	50	966.2	289.8	9.643
0.5	50	1739.1	869.5	7.500
0.5	50	1545.8	772.9	8.438
0.5	50	1352.6	676.3	9.643

Results of cyclic tests are discussed in terms of crack growth rate, which is defined by a normalised Paris law, i.e.,

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C \left(\frac{\Delta G}{G_c} \right)^m, \quad (4)$$

where a is the crack length, N is the number of cycles, ΔG is the strain energy release rate amplitude, G_c is the critical strain energy release rate associated with delamination growth, and C and m are the Paris law coefficients obtained from a best fit to experimental data.

Crack growth rates, da/dN , were calculated from the slope of crack length versus number of cycles as shown in Figure 4. Firstly, the dynamic modulus was computed from the strain data via,

$$K = \frac{1}{A} \frac{\Delta F}{\Delta \varepsilon}, \quad (5)$$

where A is the gross cross sectional area, ΔF is the load amplitude and $\Delta \varepsilon$ is the strain amplitude. The delamination length was then assumed to be directly proportional to the loss in stiffness, i.e.,

$$a = L \cdot \left(1 - \frac{K}{K_{initial}} \right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{t}{h} \right)^{-1}, \quad (6)$$

where L is the specimen gauge length and $K_{initial}$ is the initial dynamic stiffness for the undamaged specimen. Finally, the crack growth rate was obtained via a linear fit to the curve of crack length as a function of number of cycles, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Derivation of crack length and crack growth rate from dynamic modulus data (data refer to R-ratio 0.1 and load severity 60%).

The strain energy release rate amplitude, ΔG , was estimated using equations (1) and (3). Experimental results could then be presented in the form of normalised Paris plots as shown in Figure 5. Best fit Paris laws were found for each R-ratio using the least squares method, and the resulting coefficients are shown in Table 2.

Figure 5: Experimental results and best-fit Paris curve for crack growth rates in cut ply specimens.

Table 2: Paris law coefficients obtained from cut-ply fatigue tests.

R-ratio	C	m
0.1	0.0870	6.707
0.3	0.2094	10.754
0.5	2.2235	20.399

NUMERICAL METHODS

Finite element model

A finite element model of the gauge section of the specimen was built for the FE software LS-DYNA using three-dimensional (3D) hexahedral elements and appropriate boundary conditions for a state of plane stress, as shown in Figure 6. Only a quarter of the specimen was modelled due to symmetries, and only one element was required across the width after the plane stress assumption. The mesh was refined near the cut and the interface between continuous and discontinuous plies, and coarsened gradually towards the other extremities. The minimum element length was 0.03125 mm and the

maximum was 0.5 mm, while the width of the model was set to 0.2 mm. Eight-node continuum elements with user-defined cohesive laws were inserted along the interface, offsetting continuous and discontinuous plies by a nominal interface element thickness of 0.01 mm. Mass was scaled by a factor of 10^5 , which resulted in relatively short computational times while still avoiding significant dynamic effects. Since all specimens consisted of unidirectional laminates, thermal stresses have been neglected throughout.

Quasi-static tests were modelled by imposing a constant velocity in the a -direction (Figure 6) to all nodes at the end of the gauge section (i.e. 50 mm away from the cut, not shown in the figure), at a value of 1 mm/s. Cyclic tests were modelled by applying and controlling a distributed force at the end of the gauge section, as described in the next section. The applied peak forces varied according to the severity being tested, and were calculated taking into account the two planes of symmetry and the reduced width.

Figure 6: Finite element model of cut-ply specimens.

Elastic material properties for IM7/8552 plies were taken from reference [2] and are shown in Table 2. Critical fracture energies for delamination along 0° ply interfaces were obtained from a best fit to experimental mixed-mode data in [3] and are shown together with the remaining basic cohesive properties in Table 3. It should be noted that all the numerical analyses presented here were based on the literature value of G_{IIc} (i.e. 1.0 N/mm, Table 3) which was obtained from independent tests in [3].

Table 3: Elastic properties for IM7/8552 UD laminates.

E_{11}	E_{22}	E_{33}	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}	ρ
[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]				[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[g·cm ⁻³]
161000	11380	11380	0.32	0.32	0.436	5170	5170	3980	1.5

Table 4: Interlaminar cohesive properties for IM7/8552.

G_{IC}	$G_{IIc} = G_{IIIc}$	σ_I^{\max}	$\sigma_{II}^{\max} = \sigma_{III}^{\max}$	E_I	$E_{II} = E_{III}$
[N/mm]	[N/mm]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[N/mm ³]	[N/mm ³]
0.2	1.0	60.0	90.0	1.e6	1.e6

Cohesive elements under quasi-static loads

A modification of the baseline fatigue interface element formulation was proposed recently by Li et al. [4] which takes into account the enhancement in effective mode-II properties when the interface is under through-thickness compressive stresses. It is assumed that the initial cohesive stiffness and softening slope remain constant, and the effective mode-II strength is then given by,

$$\sigma_{II}^{\prime\max} = \sigma_{II}^{\max} - \eta \sigma_{33}, \quad (7)$$

where σ_{33} is the through-thickness stress, σ_{II}^{\max} is the mode-II delamination strength in the absence of through-thickness stresses, and η is the empirically derived enhancement factor. The effective critical mode-II strain energy release rate becomes,

$$G'_{IIc} = \left(\sigma_{II}^{\prime\max} / \sigma_{II}^{\max} \right) G_{IIc} . \quad (8)$$

Reference [4] shows that the experimental results for glass fibre-epoxy laminates presented in [1] are best fit with an average value of $\eta = 0.74$, which also gives a good fit for carbon/epoxy test data. Therefore this value has been adopted in the present work.

Fatigue modelling

When modelling fatigue damage accumulation and propagation over large numbers of cycles, it is impractical to analyse each load cycle individually. For constant amplitude loading, one alternative is to perform an analysis of the *envelopes* of load and deformation [5, 6]. In this case the number of cycles is assumed to increase continuously with elapsed simulation time, so that fatigue degradation can be computed at each increment based on the length of the time step. Simulation time is then treated as *pseudo-time* since it is no longer related to physical properties such as kinetic energy or strain rate.

In order to illustrate the fatigue modelling technique, we assume that the cut ply specimen depicted in Figure 6 is under a cyclic load $F(t)$ which produces an end displacement $\delta(t)$, as shown in Figure 7. Fatigue degradation will cause the crack to advance, increasing specimen compliance and hence increasing the amplitude of displacement.

The fatigue modelling approach consists in analysing only the envelopes of $F(t)$ and $\delta(t)$ in time, as shown in Figure 7. The simulation begins with an initialisation step where the load is increased gradually from zero to the peak load in the assumed cyclic regime. After a short stabilisation period, the fatigue degradation law is activated, marking the start of the fatigue analysis. The envelope of displacements then expands as the interfaces degrade and the stiffness decreases.

Fatigue degradation is computed for each interface element based on the number of cycles applied and the amplitude in strain energy release rate. The interface element formulation is based on the static model presented in [2] and the fatigue model described in [7]. The latter is briefly reviewed below.

Figure 7: Schematic evolution of forces and displacements using the cycle-jump approach in the analysis of a load-controlled test.

Fatigue interface elements

In order to account for the degradation due to fatigue loading, we introduce a fatigue damage parameter d_f in the cohesive formulation so that the total accumulated damage becomes,

$$d = d_s + d_f. \quad (9)$$

During a fatigue analysis d_f increases with an increasing number of fatigue cycles. The evolution of fatigue damage is determined by the Paris law of the material, equation (1). The peak mixed-mode strain energy release rate amplitude, G_{\max} , is obtained via the numerical integration of the mixed-mode stress-displacement history of the element. The amplitude ΔG is calculated from the user-defined load ratio, and via the Paris law a crack growth rate, i.e. da/dN , is obtained. This is then converted into a fatigue damage rate, $\partial d_f / \partial N$, which defines the increment in fatigue damage for the current time step.

The computation of damage rate is based on the crack growth rate da/dN and the length of the interface element in the direction of crack propagation, L . The number of cycles for failure of a particular interface element is given by,

$$\Delta N_f = \left(\frac{da}{dN} \right)^{-1} \cdot L. \quad (10)$$

One can then compute the fatigue damage rate necessary to fail the element in this number of cycles, i.e.,

$$\frac{\partial d_f}{\partial N} = \frac{(1-d_s)}{\Delta N_f}. \quad (11)$$

Finally, the updated fatigue damage parameter at time step t is given by,

$${}^{t+\Delta t}d_f = {}^t d_f + (\Delta t \cdot f) \frac{\partial d_f}{\partial N}. \quad (12)$$

where ${}^{t+\Delta t}d_f$ is the damage variable at the new time step, Δt is the time step size, and f is the loading frequency. The total damage is then computed with equation (9) and used to retrieve cohesive element stresses.

The degradation of cohesive element stiffness due to fatigue damage is illustrated by a representative stress-damage curve in Figure 8a. At time t the interface element has accumulated damage only due to static loading, and at time $t+\Delta t$ the first fatigue damage accumulation occurs. Cohesive stresses are then computed by considering the total damage variable $d = d_s + d_f$ in the original softening curve, as shown in Figure 8a. As a consequence of the reduction in cohesive stresses due to the presence of fatigue damage, the compliance of the interface increases resulting in larger relative displacements. Therefore the static damage variable d_s also increases slightly when fatigue damage is accumulated, as shown in Figure 8b. However, this effect has only a minor influence on the integrated strain energy release rate, thus it can be neglected.

Figure 8: Stress-damage curves showing degradation due to fatigue damage; (a) cohesive stresses in one time step and (b) effective curve after several time steps.

Mixed-mode crack growth laws

In order to account for the influence of mode-mixity on crack growth rate, at least two Paris curves are required (i.e. for modes I and II). In the current FE model implementation two mixed-mode crack growth laws are available. The first is a simple linear rule of mixtures between modes I and II [8], i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
C &= \frac{G_I}{G_I + G_{II}} C_I + \frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II}} C_{II} \\
m &= \frac{G_I}{G_I + G_{II}} m_I + \frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II}} m_{II}
\end{aligned}
\tag{13}$$

where the subscripts indicate mode-I or mode-II components.

The second option is the more sophisticated non-monotonic rule described by Blanco et al. [9], i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
\log C &= \log C_I + \log C_m \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II}} \right) + \log \frac{C_{II}}{C_I C_m} \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II}} \right)^2 \\
m &= m_I + m_m \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II}} \right) + (m_{II} - m_I - m_m) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II}} \right)^2
\end{aligned}
\tag{14}$$

where the subscript m indicates that an additional Paris law is required for mixed-mode crack growth. Because the cut ply tension tests analysed here provide pure mode-II delamination, only the mode-II Paris law was required.

Crack tip tracking

As shown in equation (10), the computation of fatigue damage rate $\partial d_f / \partial N$ is based on the length of a *single* interface element, L . This implies that only one element should be under fatigue degradation in the direction of crack propagation at any time. In other words, fatigue degradation should be applied only to the cohesive elements which are part of a crack front.

The original delamination model described in [7] was first implemented in LS-DYNA as a user-defined constitutive law for continuum hexahedral elements, in a similar way as previously reported for the discrete cohesive elements [2]. Since standard user-defined routines provide no means of locating and tracking crack fronts, the Paris law degradation had to be applied to *all* damaged interface elements instead. This version, referred to as the *original formulation*, was relatively simple to implement. However, it was found to overestimate the overall crack growth rate considerably, as will be shown later in this paper. This overestimation was also found to be dependent on the number of damaged elements ahead of the crack tip, i.e. the length of the cohesive zone. However, due to its conservative nature, this version of fatigue interface elements was applied successfully in the analysis of various test cases [7].

The implementation of a crack tip tracking capability within LS-DYNA required algorithms to be written outside the user-defined routine. This new fatigue delamination model, referred to as the *crack tip tracking formulation*, identifies crack front elements automatically at every time step. This is done by checking whether the interface element is in the vicinity of an open crack which is represented by a failed element.

In order to illustrate the effect of the crack tip tracking algorithm in a full 3D model, let us analyse the case of an interface between two homogeneous isotropic thin plates,

Figure 9. The upper plate is pulled away from the fully constrained bottom plate by the application of a cyclic point load in the out-of-plane direction.

Figure 9: Model of a laminate with circular delamination for illustration of crack tip tracking algorithm.

Only one quarter of the specimen is modelled due to symmetries, with a regular mesh. Figure 10 shows maps of interface damage after the first load cycle for both fatigue model formulations. A circular delamination is seen, surrounded by damaged cohesive elements (where $d_s > 0$) and elements under Paris law degradation (where $d_f > 0$). It can be seen that in the original formulation Paris law degradation is applied to all damaged cohesive elements, which will result in a global overestimation of crack growth rate. The crack tip tracking version correctly identifies the elements belonging to a crack front, so only one element is under Paris law degradation in the direction of delamination propagation, as initially sought.

Figure 10: Interface damage after first load cycle for (a) original formulation and (b) crack tip tracking formulation.

The use of a tracking algorithm in the analysis of the cut-ply specimens is illustrated in Figure 11 for an R-ratio of 0.1 and a load severity of 75%. In this case the process zone ahead of the delamination front comprises more than 50 elements during steady-state propagation. The application of the original formulation results in an effective crack growth rate of approximately one order of magnitude higher than the input Paris law. Although conservative, the overestimation will depend on the number of elements in the cohesive zone, which makes the method also mesh-sensitive. On the other hand, the

crack tip tracking formulation isolates the element at the delamination front so that the correct crack growth rate is observed globally.

Figure 11: Crack tip tracking algorithm applied in the analysis of a cut ply specimen (R-ratio 0.1, load severity 75%, crack length 0.9 mm).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental and numerical results for quasi-static tests are shown in Figure 12 as curves of net section stress (normalised by the average experimental failure stress) versus normalised displacement. Two sets of numerical results are shown, namely for standard and compression-corrected cohesive formulations. Although the overall behaviour is similar and there is good agreement with experimental data, the enhancement due to through-thickness compressive stresses results in a slight increase in delamination load and consequently a closer agreement with the average experimental failure load.

All cyclic tests listed in Table 1 were modelled using fatigue interface elements. Furthermore, for the case of R-ratio = 0.1 both the original and the crack tip tracking formulations were utilised for comparison.

Plots of mode-II peak strain energy release rate, $G_{II, \max}$, obtained from the numerical simulations using an R-ratio of 0.1 are shown as functions of crack length in Figure 13. All cases were marked by an initial drop in $G_{II, \max}$ and stabilisation around a 'plateau' value. This behaviour reflects the gradual formation of a damage zone ahead of the crack tip, after which damage initiation and propagation reach a pseudo steady-state.

Figure 12: Numerical and experimental curves of normalised net section stress versus normalised displacement for quasi-static cut ply tests.

Figure 13: Numerical strain energy release rate versus crack length for fatigue tests as computed with the crack tip tracking formulation.

Crack growth rates were obtained from numerical results via the analysis of the time of failure of each interface element. Time intervals between the failure of consecutive elements were converted into cycle intervals, ΔN , which were then divided by the length of the failed element to give the inverse of an effective crack growth rate. With the strain energy release rate amplitude being stored as a state variable, normalised Paris plots could be obtained as shown in Figure 14 for an R-ratio of 0.1. The results of each simulation are shown as small clouds of data points representing individual interface elements. The small variations in strain energy release rate amplitude observed in each

set of numerical results are a consequence of the initial drop in $G_{II,max}$ shown in Figure 13.

The results in Figure 14 show that the original formulation over-predicts crack growth rate especially at higher severities, since at higher loads the cohesive zones are larger with more damaged cohesive elements ahead of the crack tip. Therefore the original formulation gives an effective Paris curve which has a different slope in comparison with the input curve. On the other hand, the crack tip tracking formulation eliminates the dependency on cohesive zone length, resulting in a good fit to the input Paris curve.

Figure 14: Experimental and numerical Paris curves for an R-ratio of 0.1 using the original and crack tip tracking modelling techniques.

Cyclic tests with R-ratios of 0.3 and 0.5 were modelled using the crack tip tracking formulation only, and the results are shown as Paris plots in Figure 15. Each R-ratio required the use of its specific set of Paris law coefficients defined previously in Table 2. As expected, the use of fatigue interface elements allows the reproduction of the input Paris laws obtained experimentally.

Figure 15: Numerical and experimental Paris curves for cut ply specimens loaded under three different R-ratios (all numerical results using crack tip tracking formulation).

CONCLUSIONS

Cohesive element formulations for modelling delamination under static and fatigue loading have been evaluated via the analysis of cut ply tensile tests. For the static case, considering the interaction between through-thickness compressive stresses and mode-II interlaminar shear resulted in closer agreement with experimental results in terms of delamination load. For the fatigue case, an algorithm which identifies and tracks the location of crack fronts eliminated parasitic fatigue damage accumulation and the dependency on the length of the cohesive zone. Results for three different load ratios and various stress amplitudes show excellent agreement with the input Paris law as expected.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge Rolls-Royce Plc. for their support of this research and their permission to publish.

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